

Literature Review on Circular Economy for Plastic Products

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Abstract:

The article has reviewed the research on the circular economy, issues related to the circular economy. At the same time, we also review the research on the circular economy effect on plastic products. From previous researches on research topics, we will provide lessons for Vietnam, and orient future studies on related topics.

Key words: *Circular economy, plastic products, Vietnam.*

1. Introduction

Nowaday, plastic products is an important part of daily life. Strong, lightweight, and moldable, plastics are used in thousands of products that add comfort, convenience, and safety to our everyday lives. Plastics in carpets, blankets, and pillows keep us comfortable in our homes.

Plastic products is applied popularly in many fields such as: packaging, transportation, energy efficiency, sports, medicine, electronics... Plastic's light weight, strength, and ability to be molded into any form makes it an ideal packaging material. Plastic is used for food and non-food packaging. Advances in plastic technology has made plastic packaging more efficient: the average packaging weight for a product has been reduced over 28 percent in the last decade. Plastic packaging is convenient for consumers: clear plastic lets shoppers view the item they are purchasing and plastic packaging is easy to open. Plastic packaging protects food, medicine, and other products from contamination and germs when it is displayed and handled. Plastic also protects consumers. Plastics make up ten percent of new vehicle's total weight, and over 50 percent of their volume. Steering wheels, door liners, and stereo components are made of plastic, as are less visible parts, such as engine components. As plastic technology advances, many car companies envision using more plastic to lighten the weight of cars and trucks to make them more fuel- efficient. For every ten percent reduction in weight, a car or truck will save five to seven percent in fuel usage. Reduction in vehicle weight translates into a reduction in carbon dioxide emissions: every pound of vehicle weight that can be eliminated means 25.3 pounds of carbon dioxide emissions are saved over the vehicle's life.

Plastics can make your home more energy-efficient. Plastic sealants and caulks can seal up window leaks and plastic foam weather stripping can make doors and windows draft-free. Clear plastic sheeting for windows improves insulation and decreases drafts in the winter. Plastic blinds, window shades, and drapes help insulate windows by keeping out the sun in warm months to keep the house cooler and by keeping in heat during the winter months. Plastic awnings and reflective films also help shade the home. Many brands of high efficiency LED light bulbs are made from recycled plastic. Plastic insulation in the walls, floors, attic, and roof of your home keeps heat in during the winter and out during the summer, which saves you energy and money on your heating and cooling. Plastic foam spray fills large and small holes in walls, doors, and attics.

Plastic's strength, light weight, and moldability have revolutionized electronics. Plastic cables and cords on everything from computers to paper shredders keep electronics powered. Plastic insulation for cables and electrical equipment keeps equipment cool and protects users from over-heating. Household appliances, from toasters to DVD players, use plastic to make them lightweight and affordable. The liquid crystalline plastics in LCD flat screen televisions give beautiful pictures and save energy, using less power than traditional cathode ray tube screens. The touch screens on mobile phones, computers, and other electronics are made of polycarbonate film. The tiny microphones in mobile phones are made of polymers for their shock-resistance. Handsets and earpieces are lighter and more comfortable because of plastics.

Plastic products consumption has been growing rapidly and impacting negatively on environment, so it is necessary to find solution for this issue. A circular economy for plastic products may help reducing plastic pollution. The circular economy is gaining growing attention as a potential way for our society to increase prosperity, while reducing demands on finite raw materials and minimizing negative externalities. Such a transition requires a systemic approach, which entails moving beyond incremental improvements to the existing model as well as developing new collaboration mechanisms. The challenges and opportunities posed by the current plastics system demand fundamental change in which research and innovation (R&I), enabled and reinforced by policymaking, play a crucial role. While plastics bring benefits as a functional material, the current system has significant unintended drawbacks, including economic loss of material value and environmental damage, such as marine litter. It has become evident that the plastics economy needs to change from a system that produces waste by design to one that preserves the value and benefits of plastics, but eliminates these drawbacks.

2. Literature review

2.1. Circular economy

The circular economy is an alternative to the current linear, make, use, dispose, economy model, which aims to keep resources in use for as long as possible, to extract the maximum value from them whilst in use, and to recover and regenerate products and materials at the end of their service life. The circular economy promotes a production and consumption model that is restorative and regenerative by design. It is designed to ensure that the value of products, materials, and resources is maintained in the economy at the highest utility and value, for as long as possible, while minimising waste generation, by designing out waste and hazardous materials. The circular economy applies both to biological and technical materials. It embraces systems thinking and innovation, to ensure the continuous flow of materials through a 'value circle', with manufacturers, consumers, businesses and government each playing a significant role.

The World Economic Forum reported that material (technical and biological) cost savings of up to \$1 trillion per year could be achieved by 2025 by implementing the circular economy worldwide⁶⁴. And the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) "CEO Guide to the Circular Economy" indicates that the circular economy could help unlock USD 4.5 trillion of business opportunities while helping to fulfil the Paris Agreement⁶⁵. Implementing the circular economy across the energy, built environment, transport, and food sectors in Europe could reduce carbon emissions by 83% by 2050 compared to 2012 levels⁶⁶. A study by the Club of Rome also indicates that transitioning to a circular economy across various economic sectors in five European countries (Finland, France, the Netherlands, Spain and Sweden) by 2030 could lead to a two-thirds reduction in carbon emissions, lower business costs, and create up to 1.2 million jobs. While studies on developing countries are scarce, UNDP reported that circular economy strategies could help the Lao DPR achieve its climate mitigation targets, while also developing local industries, reducing dependency on resource rents, imported materials and products, thus helping to reduce poverty.

The circular economy is a timely and highly relevant topic. The idea behind the circular economy is that companies have a responsibility to uphold the environmental and sustainable values of society and must respond to a broad set of stakeholders rather than just their closest shareholders. This idea has resulted in research into ways management can expand and rethink the traditional make-use-dispose business model. Despite criticism of this view and debate over whether it is realistic to expect companies to venture beyond shareholders' interests when designing their business models to close resource loops and achieve the complete cycling of materials, an increasing number of scholars and practitioners are hopeful that such a transition can address what is perhaps the greatest challenge currently facing society. Recently, discussions about the importance of the circular economy have evolved. The focus of these discussions has shifted away from simplistic arguments about why the Sustainability 2018, 10, 2799; doi:10.3390/su10082799. www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability Sustainability 2018, 10, 2799 2 of 19 circular

economy is good toward understanding more theoretically sophisticated justifications for the financial outcomes of implementing circular business models. This shift is important. The field of business management and the circular economy lacks accepted theoretical perspectives that are substantial enough to outline and analyze empirical evidence and align discussions in the strategy, organization, and management literatures. The scholarly study of management may be poorly integrated with the circular economy because the concept of the circular economy is rooted in web-articles and text books rather than peer-reviewed scientific work. The circular economy has received the most attention in disciplines, like industrial ecology, production economics, and operations research. Thus, the scientific literature on the circular economy has been developed through research conducted outside the management and organizational theory tradition, with an overriding focus on problems, like waste management and recycling, that have traditionally been handled by non-profit organizations. A review of the literature reveals that few strategy, organization, or management scholars have employed the concept of the circular economy. These scholars have focused on describing different circular business models, circular business model innovations, and certain challenges and uncertainties that companies encounter when they adapt to the circular economy. Also, research on related concepts, such as product-service systems, eco-efficient services, and business model sustainability, has discussed the business practice implications of the circular economy. However, the empirical evidence from research on the circular economy has not been analyzed or synthesized from a management or organizational theory perspective, which implies a limited focus on profitability and competitive advantage. Indeed, recent reports have indicated that very few companies have managed to transform their businesses to compete with what is discussed in the circular economy literature. So, why are firms unable to transform themselves to compete with business models that are based on the circular economy, and could such a transformation lead to differences in behavior and profitability? To stimulate research in this area, we first define and afterwards review what we know about the circular economy based on diverse literature perspectives. Based on these insights, we outline the fundamentals of circular business models and provide a range of perspectives to explain why circular business models can be profitable and how it can influence competitive advantages. We explore our research question by acknowledging six theoretical perspectives to explaining differences in firms' behavior and the potential for economic returns and profitability:

- (1) Contingencies and the importance of firms' fit with the environment to exploit and create market opportunities from the circular economy;
- (2) transaction costs and contracting between partners involved in creating the circular economy;
- (3) differences in firms' resources and capabilities;
- (4) differences in network position and path-dependence logics;
- (5) industry and structural differences in terms of competition and barriers to entry; and (6) agency issues, contractual design, and customer relationships.

Accordingly, the goal of the business model shifts from making profits through the sale of products or artifacts to making profits through the flow of resources, materials, and products over time, including reusing goods and recycling resources. This reasoning implies that companies can reduce negative impacts on the environment by delivering and capturing value through this alternative value proposition. However, undertaking such ambitious transformation requires close collaboration and coordination between industrial network actors to achieve close or slow material loops. Based on these insights, we propose a circular business model definition to explain how an established firm uses innovations to create, deliver, and capture value through the implementation of circular economy principles, whereby the business rational are realigned between the network of actors/stakeholders to meet environmental, social, and economic benefits. Laws have been introduced by, for example, the European Union (EU) and the Chinese government to stimulate a transition towards a circular economy. In Europe, a Circular Economy Package has been approved in 2018 by the European Parliament that includes a range of policy measures and actions to reduce waste across Europe. For EU member states, targets have been set for the

recycling of material, including packaging, plastic, wood, ferrous metals, aluminum, glass, paper, and cardboard. Likewise, in China, a Circular Promotion Law has been passed in 2009 that promotes the efficient use of resources to protect and improve the environment. We argued that several research areas and theoretical perspectives are necessary to understand the complex tasks that companies and business practitioners face when transitioning to the circular economy. Overall, our theory review suggests that companies that enter the circular economy with innovative business models to address sustainability concerns face a highly uncertain environment. In this environment, customers and customer behaviors are sometimes unknown or undefined, and the needs of product attributes are uncertain. Furthermore, there is no clear or established value chain or value-delivery mechanism based on what has been widely researched and propagated under the traditional make-use-dispose business model. In light of this uncertainty, we suggest that companies interested in circular or sustainable business models will be at or near the forefront and will have enormous potential to stake a claim on their markets, which could lead to profits and long-term competitiveness.

3. Circular economy as solutions for the plastic sector

The Ellen MacArthur Foundation summarised the goals for a circular economy in the plastics sector as follows: improve the economic viability of recycling and reuse of plastics; halt the leakage of plastics into the environment, especially waterways and oceans; and decouple plastics production from fossil-fuel feedstocks, while embracing renewable feedstocks.

Recent science and innovation highlights examples of how these goals might be achieved:

i) Produce plastics from alternative feedstocks

Examples of alternative feedstocks include greenhouse gas such as CO₂ and methane, bio-based sources such as oils, starch, and cellulose, as well as naturally occurring biopolymers, sewage sludge and food products. Some plastics can be produced using benign and biodegradable materials. And eco-friendly alternative flame retardants have been developed which could eliminate the use of some hazardous chemicals in plastics manufacture.

ii) Use plastic waste as a resource

The capture and recovery of plastic waste for remanufacturing into new value products has been widely demonstrated, for example, for making bricks and composites, in road construction for furniture, as well as for making clothes and footwear. Plastic waste has also been converted to liquid fuel and has been burned as fuel in a waste-to-energy cycle, though there are downsides to the latter. Through chemical recycling, the petrochemical components of plastic polymers can also be recovered for use in producing new plastics, or for the production of other chemicals, or as an alternative fuel. For example, a recent study successfully developed plastics that can be chemically recycled and reused infinitely. Studies also suggest that polyethylene plastic, a significant proportion of manufactured plastics globally, can be broken down by bacteria and caterpillars, highlighting opportunities for biobased recycling of waste plastics.

(iii) Redesign plastics manufacturing processes and products to improve longevity, reusability and waste prevention, by incorporating after-use, asset recovery, and waste and pollution prevention into the design from the outset.

This means adopting a life-cycle approach including: cleaner production; discouraging single- and other avoidable plastics use; as well as designing products for appropriate lifetimes, extended use, and for ease of separation, repair, upgrade and recycling; eliminating toxic substances; and preventing the release of microplastics into the environment by redesigning products. For example, designing clothes and tires to reduce wear and tear, and eliminating, or using alternatives to, microplastics in personal care products such as toothpaste and shampoo. A further example, of redesign is the bulk delivery of cleaning and personal care products supplied with refillable plastic containers, thereby eliminating single-use bottles. Existing applications

of this model include Replenish bottles, Petainer packaging, and Splosh. Another example is reusable beverage bottles as an alternative to single-use bottles, for example, a returnable bottle system and refillable bottles, which can lower material costs and reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

(iv) Increase collaboration between businesses and consumers to increase awareness of the need for, and benefits of, a shift from non-essential plastic use and a throw-away culture, to encourage recycling, and to increase the value of plastic products, for example, by using by-products from one industry as a raw material for another (industrial symbiosis). Several analyses have highlighted the climate and environmental benefits from plastic waste recycling through industrial symbiosis. Households can be included in the symbiosis process, by strengthening waste collection systems and by creating innovative and effective take-back programs. Analysis of urban-industrial symbiosis (exchanging resources between residential and industrial areas) in a Chinese city indicated that producing energy from plastic waste led to an annual reduction in CO₂ emissions of 78,000 tonnes while avoiding the discharge of 25,000 tonnes of waste plastics a year into the environment.

(v) Embrace sustainable business models which promote products as services and encourage the sharing and leasing of plastic products

This would optimise product utilisation and increase revenue while decreasing the volume of manufactured goods. An example of this is the leasing of water dispensers and refillable plastic bottles to households and offices. Another example is the Lego's Pley system where consumers rent and return Lego sets rather than buy them.

(vi) Develop robust information platforms which provide data on the composition of plastic products, track the movement of plastic resources within the economy, support cross-value chain dialogue and the exchange of knowledge, and build on experiences gained through existing global institutional networks. An example of a global network is the RECPnet (Resource Efficient and Cleaner Production Network) that promotes resource-efficient cleaner production and facilitates collaboration including through the transfer of relevant knowledge, experiences and technologies.

(vii) Policy instruments including fiscal and regulatory measures to deal with the negative effects of the unsustainable production and use of plastics

Without these measures, markets would continue to favour fossil feedstocks, especially when oil prices are low, and the barriers to achieving the circular economy would be more difficult to overcome. Ensuring that the costs of unsustainable production and use are taken into account would encourage production from alternative less harmful sources, as well as prevent waste, and stimulate reuse and recycling. Fiscal policy measures, for example, direct surcharges, levies, carbon or resource taxes and taxes on specific types of plastic such as plastic bags, disposable cutlery and other one-use items, may be needed to discourage non-essential plastic use, and other unsustainable practices, while helping to improve the uptake, financial viability and quality of plastic recycling. Other regulatory and policy measures are needed, including recycling targets, extended producer responsibility, container deposit legislation, mandatory requirements and standards for circular/eco-design, public procurement policies, bans on landfilling and incineration, and outright bans on some plastic products, for example, single-use plastic bags.

4. Circular Economy and Circular Solutions

Following Kirzherr et al., in a circular economy, materials and products should be reused, recycled, and recovered instead of discarded, if not reduced. Companies aiming at becoming circular should offer solutions based on such activities. In order to decide what solutions could be considered circular, we turned to the literature on circular business models. In 2014, Accenture suggested five types of circular business models: circular supplies, resource recovery, product life extension, sharing platforms, and product as service. Later, Bocken et al. suggested the access performance model, extending product value, classic long life, encouraging

sufficiency, extending resource value, and industrial symbiosis as circular business model strategies. In a more systematic fashion, Lewandoski presented over 25 different business models corresponding to the ReSOLVE (regenerate, share, optimise, loop, virtualise, and exchange) framework by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation. Despite these efforts, clear definitions of circular business models and circular value propositions are still lacking. Drawing on these findings, this review focusses on the literature addressing three types of solutions, remanufactured products, product service systems (PSSs), the sharing economy, and collaborative consumption (these last two are counted as one). Remanufactured products are the result of a reuse process that repairs, replaces, or restores components of a product that is not useful anymore and aims at ensuring “operation comparable to a similar new product”. A PSS is “a market proposition that extends the traditional functionality of a product by incorporating additional services. Here, the emphasis is on the ‘sale of use’ rather than the ‘sale of product’”. Such a model enables the reuse of products by intensifying use. There are three types of PSS: product-oriented, results-oriented, and outcome-oriented, but only one could offer significant sustainability results according to Tukker and Tischner. With an outcome-oriented PSS, the company has the incentive to reduce costs, including materials, thus creating the opportunity for increased efficiency and improving sustainability. In contrast to that, the two first groups still depend on the physical product to deliver value; therefore, the potential for material efficiency might not be as considerable. Companies have implemented PSSs as a strategy to commercialise remanufactured products and intensify the use of goods, thus making it a strategy for reuse, a key activity within the circular economy.

Finally, the sharing economy and collaborative consumption are both forms of consumption that aim at intensifying the use of otherwise underutilised assets, facilitating the reuse of products as in the case of PSSs. According to the European Commission, the sharing economy refers to “companies that deploy accessibility-based business models for peer-to-peer markets and its user communities”. Schor suggested four types of activities that are considered sharing: the recirculation of goods, an intensification of use of durable goods, an exchange of services, and the sharing of productive assets. Collaborative consumption as defined by Ertz considers activities that involve consumers as both providers and “obtainers” of resources. It can be based on access and ownership transfer, either online or offline. In practice, sharing economy Sustainability 2018, 10, 2758 4 of 25 solutions and collaborative consumption solutions aim at facilitating access to underused assets via marketplaces, platforms, or networks. They are not restricted to community initiatives; there are also companies that have developed solutions based on such premises. According to Accenture, technological developments have facilitated the proliferation of the sharing economy and collaborative consumption-based solutions, as they have allowed organisations and peers to access broader markets and populations. However, and although their potential to contribute to sustainability has been an argument to promote them, there is no conclusive evidence that such a promise has been fulfilled; on the contrary, there appear to be indications that so-called sharing companies are increasing the demand for resources.

5. New plastics economy: a circular economy for plastic

5.1. The impacts of plastic product on society and environment

The benefits of plastic are undeniable. The material is cheap, lightweight and easy to make. These qualities have led to a boom in the production of plastic over the past century. This trend will continue as global plastic production skyrockets over the next 10 to 15 years. We are already unable to cope with the amount of plastic waste we generate. Only a tiny fraction is recycled. About 13 million tonnes of plastic leak into our oceans every year, harming biodiversity, economies and, potentially, our own health.

The world urgently needs to rethink the way we manufacture, use and manage plastic.

Plastics have transformed everyday life; usage is increasing and annual production is likely to exceed 300 million tonnes by 2010. In this concluding paper to the Theme Issue on Plastics, the Environment and Human Health, we synthesize current understanding of the benefits and concerns surrounding the use of plastics and look to future priorities, challenges and opportunities. It is evident that plastics bring many societal benefits and

offer future technological and medical advances. However, concerns about usage and disposal are diverse and include accumulation of waste in landfills and in natural habitats, physical problems for wildlife resulting from ingestion or entanglement in plastic, the leaching of chemicals from plastic products and the potential for plastics to transfer chemicals to wildlife and humans. However, perhaps the most important overriding concern, which is implicit throughout this volume, is that our current usage is not sustainable. Around 4 per cent of world oil production is used as a feedstock to make plastics and a similar amount is used as energy in the process. Yet over a third of current production is used to make items of packaging, which are then rapidly discarded. Given our declining reserves of fossil fuels, and finite capacity for disposal of waste to landfill, this linear use of hydrocarbons, via packaging and other short-lived applications of plastic, is simply not sustainable. There are solutions, including material reduction, design for end-of-life recyclability, increased recycling capacity, development of bio-based feedstocks, strategies to reduce littering, the application of green chemistry life-cycle analyses and revised risk assessment approaches. Such measures will be most effective through the combined actions of the public, industry, scientists and policymakers. There is some urgency, as the quantity of plastics produced in the first 10 years of the current century is likely to approach the quantity produced in the entire century that preceded.

5.2. Accumulation of plastic products waste in the natural environment

Substantial quantities of plastic have accumulated in the natural environment and in landfills. Around 10 per cent by weight of the municipal waste stream is plastic (Barnes et al. 2009) and this will be considered later in §6. Discarded plastic also contaminates a wide range of natural terrestrial, freshwater and marine habitats, with newspaper accounts of plastic debris on even some of the highest mountains. There are also some data on littering in the urban environment (for example compiled by EnCams in the UK; <http://www.encams.org/home>); however, by comparison with the marine environment, there is a distinct lack of data on the accumulation of plastic debris in natural terrestrial and freshwater habitats. There are accounts of inadvertent contamination of soils with small plastic fragments as a consequence of spreading sewage sludge (Zubris & Richards 2005), of fragments of plastic and glass contaminating compost prepared from municipal solid waste (Brinton 2005) and of plastic being carried into streams, rivers and ultimately the sea with rain water and flood events (Thompson et al. 2005). However, there is a clear need for more research on the quantities and effects of plastic debris in natural terrestrial habitats, on agricultural land and in freshwaters. Inevitably, therefore, much of the evidence presented here is from the marine environment. From the first accounts of plastic in the environment, which were reported from the carcasses of seabirds collected from shorelines in the early 1960s (Harper & Fowler 1987), the extent of the problem soon became unmistakable with plastic debris contaminating oceans from the poles to the Equator and from shorelines to the deep sea. Most polymers are buoyant in water, and since items of plastic debris such as cartons and bottles often trap air, substantial quantities of plastic debris accumulate on the sea surface and may also be washed ashore. Monitoring the abundance of debris is important to establish rates of accumulation and the effectiveness of any remediation measures. Most studies assess the abundance of all types of anthropogenic debris including data on plastics and/or plastic items as a category. In general, the abundance of debris on shorelines has been extensively monitored, in comparison to surveys from the open oceans or the seabed. In addition to recording debris, there is a need to collect data on sources; for plastic debris this should include discharges from rivers and sewers together with littering behaviour. Here, the limited data we have suggest that storm water pulses provide a major pathway for debris from the land to the sea, with 81 g m⁻³ of plastic debris during high-flow events in the USA (Ryan et al. 2009). Methods to monitor the abundance of anthropogenic debris (including plastics) often vary considerably between countries and organizations, adding to difficulties in interpreting trends. As a consequence, the United Nations Environment Programme and the OSPAR Commission are currently taking steps to introduce standardized protocols (OSPAR 2007; Cheshire et al. 2009). Some trends are evident, however, typically with an increase in the abundance of debris and fragments between the 1960s and the 1990s (Barnes et al. 2009). More recently, abundance at the sea surface in some regions and on some shorelines appears to be stabilizing, while in other areas such as the Pacific Gyre there are reports of considerable increases. On shorelines the quantities of debris, predominantly plastic, are

greater in the Northern than in the Southern Hemisphere (Barnes 2005). The abundance of debris is greater adjacent to urban centres and on more frequented beaches and there is evidence that plastics are accumulating and becoming buried in sediments (Barnes et al. 2009; Ryan et al. 2009). Barnes et al. (2009) consider that contamination of remote habitats, such as the deep sea and the polar regions, is likely to increase as debris is carried there from more densely populated areas. Allowing for variability between habitats and locations, it seems inevitable, however, that the quantity of debris in the environment as a whole will continue to increase—unless we all change our practices. Even with such changes, plastic debris that is already in the environment will persist for a considerable time to come. The persistence of plastic debris and the associated environmental hazards are illustrated poignantly by Barnes et al. (2009) who describe debris that had originated from an aeroplane being ingested by an albatross some 60 years after the plane had crashed.

5.3. Effects of plastic products debris waste in the environment and on wildlife

There are some accounts of effects of debris from terrestrial habitats, for example ingestion by the endangered California condor, *Gymnogyps californianus* (Mee et al. 2007). However, the vast majority of work describing environmental consequences of plastic debris is from marine settings and more work on terrestrial and freshwater habitats is needed. Plastic debris causes aesthetic problems, and it also presents a hazard to maritime activities including fishing and tourism (Moore 2008; Gregory 2009). Discarded fishing nets result in ghost fishing that may result in losses to commercial fisheries (Moore 2008; Brown & Macfadyen 2007). Floating plastic debris can rapidly become colonized by marine organisms and since it can persist at the sea surface for substantial periods, it may subsequently facilitate the transport of non-native or ‘alien’ species (Barnes 2002; Barnes et al. 2009; Gregory 2009). However, the problems attracting most public and media attention are those resulting in ingestion and entanglement by wildlife. Over 260 species, including invertebrates, turtles, fish, seabirds and mammals, have been reported to ingest or become entangled in plastic debris, resulting in impaired movement and feeding, reduced reproductive output, lacerations, ulcers and death (Laist 1997; Derraik 2002; Gregory 2009). The limited monitoring data we have suggest rates of entanglement have increased over time (Ryan et al. 2009). A wide range of species with different modes of feeding including filter feeders, deposit feeders and detritivores are known to ingest plastics. However, ingestion is likely to be particularly problematic for species that specifically select plastic items because they mistake them for their food. As a consequence, the incidence of ingestion can be extremely high in some populations. For example, 95 per cent of fulmars washed ashore dead in the North Sea have plastic in their guts, with substantial quantities of plastic being reported in the guts of other birds, including albatross and prions (Gregory 2009). There are some very good data on the quantity of debris ingested by seabirds recorded from the carcasses of dead birds. This approach has been used to monitor temporal and spatial patterns in the abundance of sea-surface plastic debris on regional scales around Europe (Van Franeker et al. 2005; Ryan et al. 2009).

More work will be needed to establish the full environmental relevance of plastics in the transport of contaminants to organisms living in the natural environment, and the extent to which these chemicals could then be transported along food chains. However, there is already clear evidence that chemicals associated with plastic are potentially harmful to wildlife. Data that have principally been collected using laboratory exposures are summarized by Oehlmann et al. (2009). These show that phthalates and BPA affect reproduction in all studied animal groups and impair development in crustaceans and amphibians. Molluscs and amphibians appear to be particularly sensitive to these compounds and biological effects have been observed in the low ng l⁻¹ to µg l⁻¹ range. In contrast, most effects in fish tend to occur at higher concentrations. Most plasticizers appear to act by interfering with hormone function, although they can do this by several mechanisms (Hu et al. 2009). Effects observed in the laboratory coincide with measured environmental concentrations, thus there is a very real probability that these chemicals are affecting natural populations (Oehlmann et al. 2009). BPA concentrations in aquatic environments vary considerably, but can reach 21 µg l⁻¹ in freshwater systems and concentrations in sediments are generally several orders of magnitude higher than in the water column. For example, in the River Elbe, Germany, BPA was measured at 0.77 µg l⁻¹ in water

compared with 343 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ in sediment (dry weight). These findings are in stark contrast with the European Union environmental risk assessment predicted environmental concentrations of 0.12 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ for water and 1.6 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (dry weight) for sediments.

Phthalates and BPA can bioaccumulate in organisms, but there is much variability between species and individuals according to the type of plasticizer and experimental protocol. However, concentration factors are generally higher for invertebrates than vertebrates, and can be especially high in some species of molluscs and crustaceans. While there is clear evidence that these chemicals have adverse effects at environmentally relevant concentrations in laboratory studies, there is a need for further research to establish population-level effects in the natural environment (see discussion in Oehlmann et al. 2009), to establish the long-term effects of exposures (particularly due to exposure of embryos), to determine effects of exposure to contaminant mixtures and to establish the role of plastics as sources (albeit not exclusive sources) of these contaminants (see Meeker et al. (2009) for discussion of sources and routes of exposure).

5.4. Effects on humans: Epidemiological and experimental evidence

Turning to adverse effects of plastic on the human population, there is a growing body of literature on potential health risks. A range of chemicals that are used in the manufacture of plastics are known to be toxic. Biomonitoring (e.g. measuring concentration of environmental contaminants in human tissue) provides an integrated measure of an organism's exposure to contaminants from multiple sources. This approach has shown that chemicals used in the manufacture of plastics are present in the human population, and studies using laboratory animals as model organisms indicate potential adverse health effects of these chemicals (Talsness et al. 2009). Body burdens of chemicals that are used in plastic manufacture have also been correlated with adverse effects in the human population, including reproductive abnormalities (e.g. Swan et al. 2005; Swan 2008; Lang et al. 2008).

Interpreting biomonitoring data is complex, and a key task is to set information into perspective with dose levels that are considered toxic on the basis of experimental studies in laboratory animals. The concept of 'toxicity' and thus the experimental methods for studying the health impacts of the chemicals in plastic, and other chemicals classified as endocrine disruptors, is currently undergoing a transformation (a paradigm inversion) since the disruption of endocrine regulatory systems requires approaches very different from the study of acute toxicants or poisons. There is thus extensive evidence that traditional toxicological approaches are inadequate for revealing outcomes such as 'reprogramming' of the molecular systems in cells as a result of exposure to very low doses during critical periods in development (e.g. Myers et al. 2009). Research on experimental animals informs epidemiologists about the potential for adverse effects in humans and thus plays a critical role in chemical risk assessments. A key conclusion from the paper by Talsness et al. (2009) is the need to modify our approach to chemical testing for risk assessment. As noted by these authors and others, there is a need to integrate concepts of endocrinology in the assumptions underlying chemical risk assessment. In particular, the assumptions that dose-response curves are monotonic and that there are threshold doses (safe levels) are not true for either endogenous hormones or for chemicals with hormonal activity (which includes many chemicals used in plastics) (Talsness et al. 2009).

Despite the environmental concerns about some of the chemicals used in plastic manufacture, it is important to emphasize that evidence for effects in humans is still limited and there is a need for further research and in particular, for longitudinal studies to examine temporal relationships with chemicals that leach out of plastics (Adibi et al. 2008). In addition, the traditional approach to studying the toxicity of chemicals has been to focus only on exposure to individual chemicals in relation to disease or abnormalities. However, because of the complex integrated nature of the endocrine system, it is critical that future studies involving endocrine-disrupting chemicals that leach from plastic products focus on mixtures of chemicals to which people are exposed when they use common household products.

6. Conclusion

6.1. New materials

This chapter focuses on the development of new materials, discussing fossil and renewable feedstock where appropriate. Novel plastics made from the latter often provide an insightful example of the challenges encountered. Renewable feedstock is mostly used to refer to bio-based feedstock, i.e. biomass, biomass-derived by-products, or carbon dioxide (CO₂) or methane derived from biological processes. In this report, the term is also used to denote chemicals from CO₂ or methane captured through artificial carbon capture and utilisation processes (e.g. from industrial-emissions gas or atmospheric carbon). A more in-depth look into bio-based feedstocks is given in Chapter 4. The future of innovation in new materials is driven by a few key present-day insights:

-- Plastics are synthetic alternatives to natural materials. Plastics have been on the world stage since the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th century (Morawetz, 1995). The rapid growth of plastics as everyday materials

Was driven by a need to replace natural product shortages, e.g. ivory and shellac (Pretting & Boote, 2010). Such replacement reflects Thomas Malthus's hypothesis that (unchecked) population growth always exceeds the growth of the means of subsistence (Malthus, 1798). Since its formation in 1968, the Club of Rome has presented and updated a similar hypothesis on the dwindling of the earth's resources and consequences for a growing global population (Randers, 2012 and Meadows, Randers & Meadows, 2004). To date, plastics have systematically replaced and prevented or helped avoid unsustainable use of natural materials (e.g. metals, ceramics and wood), and the production and use of plastics have grown exponentially in the last decades. Between 1950 and 2015 an estimated 8.3 billion tonnes of plastics were produced, of which 6.3 billion tonnes are considered as waste (Geyer, Jambeck & Law, 2017).

Fossil-based plastics are present all over the world. The prominent role of plastics, however, is being critically assessed as an integral part of the functioning of society (Geyer, Jambeck & Law, 2017). Today's production volumes are enabled by massive capital investments in gigantic infrastructures and operational mechanisms, rendering plastics cheap materials for mass consumption (Aftalion, 2001; Lokensgard, 2010 and Freinkel, 2011). Plastics production is part of the chemical industry that globally represents EUR 3.36 trillion in sales, with a European share of 15.1 % in 2016 down from 32.5 % in 1996 (CEFIC, 2018). The industry is fuelled by readily available and relatively cheap oil (Figure 8) and has moved from Western Europe and USA to Asia, mainly China (Figure 9). As explained in Chapter 1, not only has plastics production been globalised, but also the challenges, which is an important aspect when considering EU-wide policy.

-- Large plastics waste streams globally are associated with the packaging sector. A user trend towards more convenience combined with an increase in the living standard of a growing number of people has had a magnifying effect on plastic production. In particular, single-use packages have become a major global environmental burden (Geyer, Jambeck & Law, 2017). Packaging is the largest plastics application, currently representing 26 % of the total volume of plastics used globally and up to 40 % in Europe (World Economic Forum, Ellen MacArthur Foundation and McKinsey & Company, 2016 and PlasticsEurope, 2018). As packaging items typically have very short lifespans (Figure 10) and are directly visible to all in everyday life (Figure 11), the significant amount of plastic waste observed has become a global concern. Obviously, the economic loss and environmental damage linked to plastics go beyond packaging applications.

Accordingly, the (manufacturing) industry is trying to address the systemic issues of plastics in a number of ways, including R&I in new materials, scaling up new technologies and innovating the processing and handling of plastics.

6.2. Biological feedstock

The transition of a fossil-based economy to a biobased economy is one of the biggest industrial challenges of the 21st century. One of the prerequisites to achieving this transition and decoupling society from fossil feedstock is the development of chemicals and materials from renewable sources, in a way that does not lead to irreversible depletion of natural capital or other negative externalities. In addition, the use of renewable raw materials and resources that today are considered waste is an important part of the broader transition towards a circular economy (FP7 SPLASH and H2020 ReTAPP). Research on bio-based chemicals and plastics has increasingly been carried out in Europe, in line with the 2012 EU bioeconomy strategy, and its 2018 update, and with several bioeconomy strategies from Member States (European Commission, 2012 and European Commission, 2018a). The potential to use chemicals or materials derived from biological feedstock has already been introduced in Chapter 3. This chapter explores the availability of such feedstock, what particular precursors and materials can be derived from it, and the prospects for its products on the market, with a particular focus on plastics. Throughout this report, the term ‘bio-based’ refers to any polymer, chemical or product that is made of biomass, biomass-derived by-products or CO₂/methane derived from biological processes. In this way, bio-based feedstock is considered a subcategory of renewable or alternative feedstock, which would, for example, also include CO₂ or methane captured through artificial carbon capture and utilisation process.

More generally, in the next few years the production capacity for bio-based platform chemicals is expected to grow faster than for bio-based plastics. Between 2017 and 2022, the estimated annual global production capacity growth rate is 5-6 %, exceeding the estimations for bio-based polymers (3-4 % per year). Estimates from EU-funded projects indicate that the market potential for building blocks like fructose, succinic acid, itaconic acid and 2,5 furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA) is increasing (FP7 BIOCONSEPT, H2020 ReTAPP, FP7 TRANSBIO and FP7 SPLASH).

The market demands that the generally higher price of bio-based plastics compared to those based on fossil feedstock be justified by added value, for example better performance or environmental benefits (H2020 BIO4PRODUCTS and H2020 COSMOS). While there are exceptions, such as PEF and certain polyamides, many of the currently available bio-based plastics often struggle to meet the key requirements set for conventional plastics. This especially concerns barrier properties needed for food packaging (FP7 WHEYLAYER2). In addition, limitations in the mechanical properties are typical of some bio-based plastics (FP7 FORBIOPLAST and FP7 LEGUVAL). Moreover, there is often limited information on the differences (or similarities) in environmental or social advantages of specific bio-based polymers and chemicals compared to fossil-based counterparts. Hence, more knowledge is needed on the production of biobased polymers and chemicals with the potential to be adopted for industrial use in large-volume applications, such as food packaging and mulching film (H2020 FUNGUSCHAIN).

Develop EU-wide strategic planning for scaling biorefineries related to plastics and chemicals production. Stimulate collaboration or consolidation to create cost- efficient chemicals and plastics producing units integrated in a circular economy. This collaboration also needs to include farmers to ensure a consistent supply.

Provide information for business on the differences and similarities in performance of biobased polymers and chemicals compared to fossil-based counterparts. This information would enable better decision-making and the justification of possibly higher costs.

Set up an oversight organisation to track existing and expected inventories of non-fossil-based feedstock. In order to understand the potential and feasibility of developing bio-based platform chemicals and plastics at scale, the current and expected inventories

6.3. Business model, product and service design

In a wider perspective, materials – including plastics – are used to create products which serve the aims of a business model. Hence, to understand thoroughly how the plastics system works today, and how it could work in the future, one has to consider the related business models and product design:

-- Business models can be defined as the rationale of how an organisation creates, delivers and captures value in economic, social, cultural or other contexts (Osterwalder, Pigneur & Smith, 2010). There is a broadening understanding of the limitations of an extractive, linear economy, such as resource scarcity, coupled to an acceleration of technological disruptions. In this context, it becomes increasingly important to understand how the interactions between stakeholders are designed and can be redesigned more consciously. The process of business model construction and modification is also called business model innovation and forms part of the business strategy (Geissdoerfer, Savaget & Evans, 2017). This process is most relevant and effective when given a leading role within strategic design. The interactions described within a business model often define its innovative or even disruptive character. The business models of companies such as Netflix, AirBnB, InterfaceFLOR, Tony's Chocolonely, Uber and Facebook are disruptive not because of a technological advantage (which they rarely have), but because they changed a very specific interaction within an existing market, using technology as a tool rather than a goal.

-- Product design encompasses the development of products and services, covering a range of aspects that includes technical, economic (e.g. cost calculation, marketing and branding), human-centred (e.g. usability, ergonomics and aesthetics) and environmental ones. Modern design processes typically aim to develop new products and services that are meaningful and sustainable, and enhance human interactions. All kinds of products are developed using such an integrated product development approach, ranging from consumer goods, such as toys, to industrial products, such as medical equipment.

A circular economy pushes designers to take into account a wider spectrum of environmental, economic and social aspects of product development, which can be understood through the lens of ecodesign. While principles for 'sustainable design' have been around for over 30 years (TUDelft & UNEP, 2011), they have recently received a boost due to the increasing interest in circular economy and ecodesign guidelines. The ecodesign discipline aims to make all design considerations systemic, including the impact of all stages of a product life – from the extraction of raw materials (e.g. oil, biomass or recycled material) to the after-use phase, and the generation of energy required along the way. The materials and energy needed are then part of production, packaging, distribution, use, maintenance, and finally reuse, repair, recycling, or disposal options. Hence, when implementing ecodesign, the designer relates all choices during the development of a product to the environmental impact for the complete life cycle of a product. By adopting such a holistic perspective on product design, ecodesign guidelines are thus aligned with the principles of a circular economy (ISO/TR 14062:2002, 2002 and Van Doorselaer & Dubois, 2018). This close connection between ecodesign and the circular economy is also reflected in the EU action plan for the Circular Economy (European Commission, 2015b).

6.4. Circular after –use pathway for plastic products

In 2016 plastics demand in Europe was 50 million tonnes, of which roughly 40% were used in packaging (PlasticsEurope, 2018). This total demand is made up of 80 % thermoplastics such as PP, PE and PET, 15 % thermosets that cannot be remoulded or reheated, such as polyurethane (PU), epoxy resins, and phenolics, and 5 % of other, specialised materials. There is a well-established impression that the after-use collection, sorting and recycling systems of most, if not all, of these materials are underperforming. Often this is attributed to the increased material diversity and complexity, especially in comparison to other more homogeneous materials such as metals or glass (Esbensen & Velis, 2016 and Deloitte Sustainability, 2017). The rate of collection for recycling varies considerably across Europe, even within the same polymer type. For example, this rate ranges from 0 % for PET household films to 80 % for PET household bottles. As collection and sorting are crucial for after-use reprocessing, this chapter aims to provide further insights into this situation.

Collection and sorting across different regions

The capacity for collection, sorting and recycling differs across Europe and is insufficient to transition towards a circular economy for plastics. While collection and sorting are essential requirements to retain the value of products and materials, the existing infrastructure is insufficient in several places, or it needs to be modernised to enable high-quality recycling (European Commission, 2018j). As reflected in recent policymaking, separate collection of different material streams and investment in further sorting and recycling capacity are considered important, while avoiding infrastructural overcapacity for processing mixed waste, e.g. incineration (European Commission, 2018h and European Commission, 2018j).

Collection and sorting performance depends on a complex and continuously evolving plastics landscape. There are thousands of different plastics and additives, and there is increasing consensus that this complexity, especially in packaging, hinders effective source separation. Citizens seem to be puzzled about the many materials and formats, such as plastics films which are often not collected for recycling. In addition, the materials landscape is evolving constantly due to both established and emerging socioeconomic and material-level innovation trends, including.

-- Lightweighting. Examples include the replacement of metals (e.g. steel and or aluminium) with composites that are lighter, cheaper and can be formed into more complex shapes, and the replacement of glass beer bottles with plastic ones due to convenience and shatter-resistance (Farmer, 2013). Another example is the use of thinner PET water bottles, reducing resource use and greenhouse gas emissions, but also making recycling less attractive.

-- New materials and manufacturing techniques. Lighter or new materials are often a result of new production technologies, including additive manufacturing, a combination of advanced composite materials with computational-aided engineering for structural property optimisation, and other novel approaches (Zhu, Li & Childs, 2018). There are continuous efforts in the direction of new materials. For example, in the case of polyolefins where HDPE provides new possibilities for lightweighting of blow-moulded rigid packaging (Sherman, 2014). Innovation trends affecting packaging include nanotechnology, active and intelligent packaging (e.g. indicating food freshness) and bio-based and/or biodegradable plastics. Other factors are decentralisation, localisation and down-scaling of manufacturing trends such as 3D-printing, and the emergence of wearables creating a new category of complex products, i.e. electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) incorporated into clothes (Farmer, 2013).

-- New business models and societal trends. Changing food production, evolving cooking and eating lifestyles, international shipments and e-commerce, augmented reality and quick response codes; all these things introduce new needs for packaging. In addition, the aging European population, migration, urbanisation and adoption of global consumer values about what constitutes prosperity and well-being, all impact the type of plastics produced, used and disposed of.

-- Global trade. Increased manufacturing outside Europe and imports, and international fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) introduce increased challenges and questions on how to control waste material flows (Farmer, 2013).

These developments may affect plastic waste composition in a combination of ways. In the case of packaging, i.e. the largest plastics application in Europe and globally, the consumer goods and retail sectors play a critical role in the selection of materials. These sectors use packaging beyond preservation of content, and extend its function to communication and advertisement.

There is, however, clear evidence that in settings lacking specific (financial) incentives for citizens, such as deposit-refund schemes, most material is captured by variations of commingled collection (Palmer, Ghita, Savage & Evans, 2009). In addition, detailed studies on Dutch PET recycling have found major differences in

the composition of PET bottle products sourced from different collection systems (van Velzen, Brouwer & Molenveld, 2016). The deposit-refund schemes achieved higher-quality recyclate in comparison to separate collection and mechanical recovery schemes. Indeed, Dutch PET bottle products that originated from separate collection and mechanical recovery contained more contaminants and non-food PET flasks, barrier bottles, opaque PET bottles and non-bottle PET. In general, PET bottle products from Dutch deposit-refund systems contained few contaminants. This is attributed to the fact that the design of nearly all the bottles complied with the European PET Bottle Platform design guidelines and the products were subject to few sorting faults.

Improving collection and sorting through innovation

State of Play Extended producer responsibility schemes for plastic products are in place across Europe, but implementation and scope differ widely. EPR schemes extend the producer responsibility to the after-use stage of a product's life cycle (see also Section 5.2). Such schemes exist, for example, for vehicles, electronic equipment and packaging. However, multiple non-standardised implementation schemes apply, with substantial differences between countries and sectors. There is experience with additional and/or narrower waste streams in certain countries. For example, only eight countries cover agricultural plastic films, Belgium covers disposable kitchenware and France covers textiles and furniture (Deloitte, 2014). Producer responsibility of the industries required to take part in EPR schemes is typically implemented as collective, rather than individual, via the setting up of collective producer responsibility organisation (PRO) schemes (Deloitte, 2014). The fees contributed by the PROs tend to cover all or a substantial part of the waste collection and reprocessing system as a net separate collection and treatment cost. Over time, their scope has extended well beyond financial and cash flow management into operational interventions, including data management, organising operations, launching bids and communication campaigns.

Processing technology for after-use product handling is mainly focused on existing fossil-fuel-based plastic products. The driver of this focus seems to be dealing with the existing after-use products. Among the many projects, a few are FP7 POLYMARK, which aims to facilitate plastic waste identification for easier sorting, FP7 SUPERCLEANQ, which is developing quality control procedures for plastic waste, and FP7 ULTRAVISC, which is developing an ultrasonic detection technology.

New methods can increase the performance of separation, enabling sorting of materials currently out of scope in most markets. Novel systems can reach the (current) benchmark for separation accuracy up to 5-6 kg/m³ (FP7 W2Plastics). However, if the feed rate exceeds what a particular device is designed for, quality drops sharply and this affects the quality of the subsequently recycled material. Cross-contamination can therefore be significant, e.g. 4-5 % HDPE in PP and 8-10% PP in HDPE (FP7 W2Plastics). Improving the spectroscopic methods (e.g. through infrared, Raman or UV-VIS spectroscopy) can increase accuracy and help increase the types of polymers in scope for automated sorting

Mechanical Recycling

There is untapped potential in the current recycling system, and with technical improvements the ability to process used plastics can even increase and generate further benefits. However, high-quality mechanical recycling is impaired by the increasing complexity of the material and products landscape. For example, recycling challenges are posed by composites, thermosets, multilayers, inks, labels and adhesives. Furthermore, multiple grades and the presence of additives mean that below-virgin quality is an inherent property of mechanically recycled polymers. This lower quality makes it difficult for mechanically recycled plastics to compete with virgin feedstock or to fulfil regulatory requirements. R&I can help to overcome this barrier, for example, by designing materials and products better suited for recycling, and by developing and piloting high-quality recycling and decontamination technologies.

In addition, the price difference between virgin and recycled plastics is a crucial challenge. One reason for this situation is the underdeveloped European market for recycled plastics – a result of the past reliance on exports

of after-use plastics. This could be partly addressed by growing the market for recycled plastics with active efforts to identify new outputs and applications based on better matching of quality and demand. However, even if the market develops and scale increases, mechanical recycling faces a cost challenge as long as externalities are not accounted for. Fiscal measures addressing the costs of negative externalities, such as greenhouse gas emissions, could help to overcome the price challenge. Policymakers can further support a well-functioning secondary materials market through facilitating matchmaking (e.g. EU-wide standard for recycled grade qualities), harmonising existing legislation (e.g. on legacy additives), ensuring sufficient sorting and recycling capacity, and developing a favourable regulatory framework (e.g. mandatory level of recycled content for certain applications while safeguarding health). R&I should focus on understanding the mechanisms, routes and systemic reasons for the successful use of recycled plastics in certain applications, and its replication potential.

Chemical recycling

Solvent-based purification and depolymerisation are two reprocessing technologies that use chemical agents or processes that directly affect either the formulation of the plastic or the polymer itself. They can complement mechanical recycling because they produce (near) virgin-grade polymers from after-use plastics. Since they can remove additives and contaminants and generate 'as-new' polymers, they could play a role in creating an effective after-use economy for plastics. Most efforts are still at research or pilot stage, however, and more insight is needed into how competitive they will be at industrial scale, what the environmental impact would be, and how to best integrate them into the existing collection and recycling infrastructure.

Pyrolysis and gasification transform plastics and most of its additives and contaminants into basic chemicals, which can be refined into new materials using the existing petrochemical industry infrastructure. Their main advantage is that they can handle mixed and contaminated input, which in the current plastics system is produced in high volumes (e.g. as rejected residue in plastics recycling facilities). However, there is no guarantee that the output chemicals will be converted to new materials, given the environmental considerations such as energy requirements. In fact, the output from pyrolysis can also be used as a fuel, which is mostly how it is used today. In this case, pyrolysis and gasification, if scaled-up, would only propagate a linear fossil-based plastics economy, including several of the challenges faced today. This prompts a systemic assessment of the potential role of these technologies in the after-use system, and providing innovation support according to its findings.

In general, in a plastics economy that generates a large amount of materials that are difficult to treat with mechanical recycling, chemical recycling technologies can be complementary for two main reasons. Firstly, they are able to generate virgin-quality recycled materials. Secondly, they can process material streams which are mixed, contaminated or of unfeasibly low volume (e.g. novel materials). However, many questions remain about how to make chemical recycling work at scale, from a market, infrastructure and legislative perspective, and what the overall economic, environmental and social impacts are. To gain clarity, policymakers should stimulate further innovation and revise the regulatory landscape, including the legal status of different output materials, based on an impact analysis compared to alternatives. As with all after-use options, the performance of chemical recycling and the extent of value creation are subject to the design and material choice of plastic items put on the market – an insight that reinforces the importance of the upstream design of and innovation in new business models, products and materials.

Organic recycling and biodegradation

Composting and other organic recycling, such as anaerobic digestion, fit into a circular economy through the idea of closing the biological loops. Compostable plastics can support the organic recycling of biowaste, if the material has the right biodegradation properties and adequate infrastructure is present (e.g. collection of food leftovers). Under the assumption there is a clear link to environmental safety, biodegradable plastics could play a role in particular applications. Hence, rather than being widely applicable, general solutions for waste

treatment, compostability and biodegradability should be considered for specific situations and applications, generating particular benefits.

There is still confusion and lack of understanding about compostable and biodegradable plastics, and their possible role in a circular economy. Policymakers could create clarity for citizens and business alike by enforcing correct communication, validated by third parties, and providing guidance on applications where the use of compostable or biodegradable plastics would be appropriate. Furthermore, understanding can be improved by communication about and further development of test methods and international standards on how to determine compostability and biodegradability in specific environments, and across different environments. The organisation of such standards should be harmonised, and could explore using a horizontal method (i.e. one standard for all products in a specific environment). Adequate collection and sorting infrastructure is another requirement to avoid cross-contamination with other recycling routes. In addition, different policy measures, including legislation, should be harmonised to provide a clear direction for R&I in, and implementation of, compostable or biodegradable materials.

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